

A-nor-Triterpenoid from *Zizyphus jujuba*

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A triterpenoid A-norlupa-2,20-diene-14,17-dicarboxylic acid has been isolated from the leaves of *Zizyphus jujuba*.

Isolation of a wide variety of chemical constituents including peptides¹ and triterpenoids² was reported earlier from *Zizyphus jujuba* Lam. (Rhamnaceae) by other workers. We reported³ the isolation from the same source (bark) of lupeol, betulinic acid and ceanothic acid besides a unique compound, zizyberanolic acid which was the first naturally occurring pentacyclic triterpenoid having a formyl and a hydroxyl group in vicinal arrangement on a five-membered ring. Further studies on the leaves of the plant revealed the occurrence of yet another triterpenoid, A-norlupa-2,20-diene-14,17-dicarboxylic acid (**1**), the characterisation of which is reported in the present communication

Hexane-EtOAc eluates of the petrol-ether extract of the leaves of *Z. jujuba* on rechromatography over silica gel afforded a material when the column was eluted with a mixture of hexane-ethyl acetate (3 : 1). The compound was crystallized from Me₂CO-EtOAc, m.p. 358–60°. This triterpenoid (**1**), C₂₉H₄₂O₄ (M⁺ 454) displayed ir bands for two carboxylic acid groups (1688 and 1693 cm⁻¹), an *exo*-methylene (890 cm⁻¹) and a *cis*-disubstituted-ethylenic linkage⁴ (755 cm⁻¹). The ¹H nmr spectrum of the compound was informative and revealed all the structural features of the molecule. It showed, besides other signals in the ¹H nmr spectrum (200 MHz, DMSO-d₆), the resonances for a vinylic methyl (δ 1.6, 3H, s), *exo*-methylene protons (δ 4.55, 4.66, m, =CH₂) and two protons on a *cis*-disubstituted double bond (δ 5.41, 5.96, 2H, d, each, *J* 5.62 Hz). The latter signals are in accord with the presence of vicinal vinyl hydrogen atoms.

The presence of two carboxyl groups, early detection of which was obtained from the ir spectrum, was confirmed from ¹³C nmr spectrum (δ 176.9 and 177.4). Comparison of ¹³C nmr spectral data of **1** (50 MHz, DMSO-d₆) suggested its close similarity with zizyberanolic acid³ (**2**) and ceanothic acid³ (**3**) except that the extruded carbon atom either in the former or in the latter is absent in **1**. It is plausible that the extruded C-1 carbon atom in **2** and **3** has been eliminated in the formation of **1**. This should, therefore, contain C₂₉-carbon atoms which was confirmed from mass, ¹³C nmr and DEPT.

Thus, **1** appeared to be mono-nor-triterpenoid of the lupeol series containing two carboxyls, a *cis*-disubstituted double bond and another double bond in an isopropenyl system. The presence of two vicinal vinyl hydrogen atoms (δ 140.8, d, C-2; 138.7, d, C-3) and an isopropenyl group

(δ 20.4, q, C-30; 110.1, t, C-29 and 150.0, s, C-20) was confirmed from ¹³C nmr spectrum. The ¹³C nmr spectral data of the compound have been completely interpreted and assigned (vide Experimental). The ¹³C nmr spectral analysis of **1**, a triterpenoid of the modified A-nor-lupane series, is being reported for the first time. These data suggested its identity with A-nor-lupa-2,20-diene-14,17-dicarboxylic acid (lit.⁴ m.p. 354°) which was isolated⁴ previously from *Ceanothus americanus* (Jersey tea). This constitutes the second isolation of **1** from a natural source and first from genus *Zizyphus*. Finally, the structure **1** was confirmed from its mass spectral fragmentation pattern. The genesis of the important ion peaks at *m/z* (rel. int.) 454 (M⁺, 9.1), 439 (17.0), 393 (27.4), 371 (44.7), 175 (62.8), 161 (30.5), 107 (100.0), 93 (63.1), 91 (84.5), 69 (40.7), 55 (66.5) and 41 (70.3) could be best explained in terms of the assigned structure **1** for the nor-triterpenoid.

Experimental

Plant material was collected locally and identified⁵. M.p. is uncorrected. ¹H nmr (200 MHz) and ¹³C nmr (50 MHz) spectra were recorded in DMSO-d₆. Silica gel (B.D.H., 60–120 mesh) and silica gel G (Merck) were used for cc and tlc respectively. Sample was routinely dried over P₂O₅ for 24 h.

The air-dried leaves (2 kg) of *Z. jujuba* were kept soaked in petroleum ether in a percolator for one month. The crude petrol extract obtained after evaporation of the solvent was chromatographed over silica gel and the column was eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. Concentrated hexane-EtOAc (3 : 1) eluates were subjected to re-chromatography over silica gel using the same solvent (hexane-EtOAc, 3 : 1) elution technique. The latter fractions of the column on concentration gave a material which was crystallized from Me₂CO-EtOAc mixture to afford **1**, m.p. 358–60°; R_f 0.28 (hexane : EtOAc, 1 : 1, Si-gel) and 0.32 (hexane : EtOAc, 1 : 3, Si-gel); ν_{max} 1688, 1693, 890

and 755 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 0.86 (3H, s), 0.91 (3H, s), 0.94 (6H, s), 1.62 (3H, s), 4.55 and 4.66 (2H, m, =CH₂), 5.41 and 5.96 (1H, d, each, J 5.62 Hz, H-2 and H-3); ^{13}C nmr δ 140.8 (d, C-2), 138.7 (d, C-3), 44.4 (s, C-4), 62.4 (d, C-5), 17.1 (t, C-6), 22.5 (t, C-7), 50.2 (s, C-8), 46.8 (d, C-9), 38.2 (s, C-10), 25.3 (t, C-11), 27.5 (t, C-12), 38.9 (d, C-13), 55.2 (s, C-14), 34.1 (t, C-15), 36.6 (t, C-16), 58.8 (s, C-17), 51.0 (d, C-18), 47.3 (d, C-19), 150.0 (s, C-20), 29.9 (t, C-21), 37.0 (t, C-22), 29.5 (q, C-23), 17.7 (q, C-24), 21.3 (q, C-25), 18.6 (q, C-26), 177.0 (s, C-27), 177.4 (s, C-28), 110.0 (t, C-29), 20.0 (q, C-30); m/z (rel. int.) 454 (M^+ , 9.1), 439 (17.0), 393 (27.4), 371 (44.7), 175 (62.8), 161 (30.5) 107 (100.0), 93 (63.1), 91 (84.5), 69 (40.7), 55 (66.5) and 41 (70.3).

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